

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B363
Date: 06 May 2008
Take Off: 15:14:00Z
Landing: 18:24:34Z
Flight Time 3h 10

Campaign: EUCAARI

Operating Area: Rotterdam – Melpitz - Oberpfaffenhofen

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Megan Northway	University of Reading	Y
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	N
6	CCN / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	N
7	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM	Y
8	Wet & Dry Neph / PSAP / Filters / CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	Only PSAP
9	SWS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	Y
10	AMS	Paul Williams	University of Manchester	N
11	2D-S / CAPS / CPI	Dan Tong	University of Manchester	N
12	PAN / Core Chem	Jim McQuaid	University of Leeds	N,y
13	Mission Scientist 2	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester	

Flight Track:

B363 Track 06-MAY-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B363
 Date: 06 MAY 2008
 Project: EUCAARI
 Location: Rotterdam - Melpitz - Oberpfaffenhofen

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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144130		Start-Up	-.31 kft	359	51'56.98N, 4'26.15E
151011		ASP	-.30 kft	359	Open
151400		T/O	1.2 kft	359	Rotterdam
151614	155619	Run 1	2.0 kft	359	2.3k', QNH 1024 hPa
153028		Event	2.0 kft	359	QNH 1023
153706		Event	2.0 kft	359	E1
154500		Video	2.0 kft	359	Start FFC & UFC
154735		Event	2.0 kft	359	F4
155116		Event	2.0 kft	359	F5
155620	155626	Event	2.0 kft	359	Climb to 3.2k'
155722	160920	Run 2	2.9 kft	359	3.2k' End at F7
155845		Event	2.9 kft	359	F6
160119		Event	2.9 kft	359	Heimann cal
161010	162331	Run 3	3.5 kft	359	3.8k'
162440	165710	Run 4	2.4 kft	359	2.7k', end over Melpitz
164135		Event	2.4 kft	359	F8
164251		Event	2.4 kft	359	Passed power plant?
164324		Event	2.4 kft	359	Close filter inlets
165021		Event	2.4 kft	359	Abeam F9
165950	170504	Profile 1.1	2.4 - 7.6 kft	359	Sawtooth, 2.7k'- 8k'
170505	170956	Profile 1.2	7.6 - 3.4 kft	359	8k' -3.7k'
170548		Event	7.3 kft	359	Abeam F9
170957	172225	Run 5	3.4 kft	359	3.7k'
171446		Video	3.4 kft	359	Change Tapes
172203		Event	3.4 kft	359	A33
172304	181305	Run 6	4.0 - 3.4 kft	359	4.3k', Q1023
173852		Event	4.0 kft	359	Ease down to 4k'
173913		Event	3.7 kft	359	Level at 4k'
174216		Event	3.8 kft	359	A54
175352		Event	3.7 kft	359	Ease down
175413		Event	3.3 kft	359	Level at 3.6k'
175751		Event	3.4 kft	359	A55
180739		Event	3.3 kft	359	Light rain
180831		Event	3.4 kft	359	Q1022
182434		Land	1.6 kft	359	Oberpfaffenhofen
182551		ASP	1.6 kft	359	Close
182830		Shutdown	1.6 kft	359	48'05.10N, 11'17.65E

B363 Track 06-MAY-08

**EUCAARI Flight B363 (dual flight with B362)
FAAM sortie brief**

Tuesday 6 May, 2008

1. Pilot 1 (Directflight)
2. Pilot 2 (Directflight)
3. CCM (Directflight)
4. Core Chemistry - (FAAM)
5. Flight Manager - (FAAM)
6. Cloud Physics – (FAAM)
7. SWS – Debbie O’Sullivan (MO)
8. CPI rack – Dantong Liu (Manchester)
9. wet nephelometer/filters – James Bowles (MO)
10. AMS Rack – Paul Williams (Manchester)
11. CCN – Jamie Trembath (FAAM)
12. Mission Scientist – Hugh Coe (Manchester)
13. Mission Scientist 2 – Megan Northway (Reading)

Operating Area: Rotterdam to Oberpfaffenhofen following low level routes: #1 (eastbound to Melpitz); #6 southbound to Oberpfaffenhofen.

Sortie Objectives: To map out pollution outflow from Central Europe towards the UK and North Sea area and investigate the radiative properties of aerosol particles over the southern North Sea.

Weather. Atlantic low positioned west of Iceland (978 mbar) and High over Denmark, extending North-South from Norway and into Germany. A cold front associated with the low will extend N-S across the Irish Sea to Biscay, held stationary by high.
Anticyclonic flow from Central Europe expected to enter southern North Sea during the day.

Flight patterns:

1. Given clear skies (no clouds to interfere with direct radiation) prior to take-off perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
2. Take off Rotterdam at 15Z
3. Profile from 5000’ to 2000’ and follow route #1 from Rotterdam east to Melpitz. Follow route #6 south to Oberpfaffenhofen. Flight level in layer at aerosol maximum, some sawtooths to be performed where possible.
[3 hr 15 min]
4. Land at Oberpfaffenhofen (expected touchdown 1815Z, 2015 local)
[3 hr 15 min]

Other comments:

Science power required at Rotterdam during refuel.

FAAM Sortie Debrief

Flight Number B363 EUCAARI (dual with B362)

Tuesday 6 May, 2008

Mission Scientist - Megan Northway

Sortie Objectives: To map out the mixed aged and fresh pollution in central Europe moving towards the UK and the North Sea area.

Operating Area: Rotterdam to Oberpfaffenhofen following low level routes:#1 (eastbound to Melpitz); #6 (southbound to Oberpfaffenhofen).

Weather: Atlantic low positioned west of Iceland (978 mbar) and high over Denmark, extending North-South from Norway and into Germany. A cold front associated with the low will extend N-S across the Irish Sea to Biscay, held stationary by high. Anticyclonic flow from central Europe expected enter southern North Sea during the day.

Flight Patterns: Take-off from Rotterdam was at 15:15Z after a quick refuel. An SLR was immediately commenced at 2300 ft from Rotterdam to E1->F4->F5. Altitude was adjusted several times on the track F6->F7-F8 to stay at the minimum 2000 ft a.g.l. Going east towards the Dutch/German border on this track aerosol values increased steadily to over $100 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ (blue) on the nephelometer near F8. Shortly after passing F8, a large coal plant was spotted almost directly below the flight track which (given the easterly winds) was likely responsible for the elevated aerosol values. The plume from this plant extended almost up to the flight level at 2700 ft. AMS saw values up to $26 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ organics, $17 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{NO}_3$ and $26 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{SO}_4$. After passing the plume, aerosol values sharply decreased. At Melpitz, a profile sawtooth was completed to 8000 ft and back down to 3700 ft. The top of the aerosol plume was near the top of the profile at 8000 ft. Conditions south of Melpitz were clean at 4000 ft through A54 and A55 with the exception of one refinery plume sampled around 18:05Z. This was likely due to the light rain encountered at the end of the flight. A final profile climb to 7000 ft ended science for the day.

Summary: A good flight for surveying the aged and fresh pollution in Holland, and northern and eastern Germany. A coal plant plume (brown coal?) was sampled near waypoint F8 which has high levels of SO_4 , Organics, and NO_3 .

Instrument Problems: PSAP connectivity at the beginning of the flight. AMS reported low sensitivity (due to a heater bias issue) for first two hours of the flight. Upper SHIMS was rebooted during the flight. SMPS instrument did not work at the highest levels of the flight.

Total column of AN-SO4 for age class all
Analysis @ 20080518. 90000 Actual @ 20080506.1500

Total Cloud Cover
VT: Tue, 06 May 2008, 12 UT (+24 h)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.363** Date 6 May 2008 Name Megan Northway Page 1 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
15:15z					T/O Rotterdam
15:16:14	R1	2900ft			2900
15:33					PSAP CCN connection problem - not working
15:37					SP2 seeing not a lot of BC
15:42	R1	2250	East 54° E		CCN attempting to fix PSAP
15:47:35			76°		Passing waypoint F4
15:51:16	R1	2200	136		passing waypoint F5, turning SE
15:52	R1	2200	139		passing ^{power(?)} plant to left, ^{town of} Zost (sp?)
		3200			climbing to 3200 to stay stay
15:57:22	R2	3200			2000 ft above terrain
~16:00	R2	"			PSAP back online, CCN offline
~16:04		"			snapped photos of windfields below + hills
16:10					climbing to 3500'
~16:10	R2	"			CCN back online
16:10:10	R3	3800			more terrain - climbing to 3800
					bimodal smps, AMS load. 95: 32 NO ₃ 250y, 0.30rg 49mg
16:19	R3	3400 3800	(E) 90°		CCN also tracking nephelometer
					descending to 2700 ft
16:24	R4	2700			
16:28		2700			filters going on for ~30 min
					nephelometer going up + CO
16:33	R4	"			turning to avoid traffic

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B363**... Date 6 May 2008 Name Megan Noethling Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
16:34	R4	2700	99		Some str-cum above, murky ^{down} visibility towards Melpitz (~40mi)
16:35		2700	99		# SP2 scattering particles have doubled absorbing particles the same
16:36		"	91		nephelometer has increased + NO/NO ₂ /CO neph > 110 m-1
16:43					passing wp + F8
16:44		"	90		large cloud ^(?) plant to left, probably we have been sampling it for some time
					nar. filter may be stuffed.. given winds - smoke puff seems to come almost to our altitude
16:45	R4	"	90		things now much cleaner
		"	345		passing F9, turning left (N)
16:52	"	"	345		plume organic loading 17 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NO ₃ 6.8 SO ₄ 14.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ - 16:33 - powerplant? 16:35 org
16:56	R4	"			1 mile away from Melpitz ^{towards}
16:56:55	ended R4	"			cloud , turn to left (SE)
16:59:50	PL1	2500- 8000	152		Sawtoothingly to 8000 ft, avoiding cloud.
					aerosol decreased some, to 10 m-1 in Blue neph.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.363** Date 6 May 2008 Name Megan Noethling Page 3 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
17:05:05	P1.2	8000ft 3.7kt			
17:05:48		3700			passing FA
17:09:57	R5	3700			
17:22:03	"	3700			passing A33, near some convective cloud above us
17:23:04	R6	4300ft			↙ passing down to avoid cloud
17:40	"	4000ft			→
1743	"	4000			AMS had poor sensitivity for the past few hours - has now changed for the better - something to do w/ heater bias
1750	"	4000ft			pretty clear conditions here
1759	"	3600			running last filter, passing down
					Horace won't plot anything before 17:09 now - may have biased a few of my plots as I did ^{did} not notice ^{notice} for awhile starting at the most recent data for
18:05	"	3600			possible refueling plane? - filters off
18:10					light rain - closed PSAP values
18:12	"	3600			still rain
18:13:05	"	"			" " end of run 6
18:13					end of science climb to 7000ft, end of science
18:25	—				landing at sunset, nearly dark

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B363** Date 6/5/08 Name HUGH COE Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					ROTTERDAM via TO OP VIA
					MELPITZ.
					LOW LEVEL IN SITU AEROSOL SAMPLING
15:14:02					T/O ROTTERDAM
15:16:14	RUN1	2500ft			
15:29:20					PSAP Down cable base in base toolkit sent to front for CEN to repair.
					continue at same level.
15:35		2800'			$\sigma_{BASE} \sim 100 Mm^{-1}$
					$\sigma_{RED} \sim 45 Mm^{-1}$ fairly constant but inc a little
					crossing German / Dutch border
15:36:39					E1/FS point passed.
15:40					Leading now falling $\sigma_{BASE} \sim 50 Mm^{-1}$ and $\sigma_{RED} \sim 30 Mm^{-1}$.
					Some scattered cum low but mostly cloud free
15:47:34					Waypoint F4.
15:51:10					Waypoint F5.
15:56:19	SPD R1	2000'			} adjustment for terrain
15:57:22	SPD R2	3200'			

18-13

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.363** Date 6/5/08 Name H. Cox Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
15:58:43					aerosol scattering decreased
					$\sigma_{\text{blue}} \sim 60 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$ (blue) to
					30 Mm^{-1} (when inc alt.
					Visually much clearer here
					PSAP & CCN CPC now
					fixed by CCN operator - good mail.
16:09:20	END R2	3200'			F7 achieved and end of run 2,
16:10:10	R3	3800'			start R3.
16:16:00					Ams: 0.2; 0.4; 0.3 NO_2 , SO_2 , O_3
					SMPS bin mode
16:23					over central Germany; cloud
16:23:31	END R3				free; little pollution $\sim 40 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$
					σ_{blue}
					descent due to red alt.
16:24:40	START R4	2700			Start of fillers
					aerosol inc. now
					scattering goes up
16:37					SP2 scattering particles inc
					but BC not increased high
					scattering
					12ph σ_{blue} up to 100 Mm^{-1}
16:41:30					Wavelength FB
16:43			51° 10'	12° 30' E	Past over a large Power Plant
					Plume; wind direction likely

we have sampled this
plume for last 200 miles.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.363** Date 6/5/08 Name HUGH COE Page 3 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
16:46:43					no post post plots
					and aerosol levels fallen
					to very low levels clear
					again
				@16:34	17 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ org
					6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ no3
					14.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ sulphate.
				@16:35	26.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ org
					17 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ no3
					26.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ sulphate
					Sawtooth over Melpitz.
16:56:57		2400'			MELPITZ Overhead.
16:59:58	PI.1	2700' - 8000'			Start of sawtooth run.
17:05:08	PI.2	8000' - 2700'			At 8000' not quite at top
					of aerosol layer clouds
					tops just above; appears
					more aerosol to east but
					sun to west.
17:08:44 17:08:44	end PI.2 START 25	3100'			reph remains at 30 m^{-1} .
17:22:25	END 25	.			
17:23:04	START 26	4300'			
					Weather clearer to east.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B363** Date 6/5/08 Name H. CCE Page 4 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
17:03:00					AMS reports heater bias shifted for last 2 hours resulting in a loss of sensitivity.
	Instrument report				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SWS fast fine • Upper SWMS lost a little bit at start but rebound and OK • Cloud Phys. OK • Coe Chem - fine • TDLAS Screen suggest rubbish • PAN rubbish same as before • CAPS / SP2 SP2 worked well. • CAPS seems OK but needs check. • CCN slight prob with software but OK now; CPC looks better after earlier prob. • AMS loss of sensitivity but ok otherwise • SMPS OK low level but no good at high level • Wet rep; dry rep. • filters • BSAP repaired.
17:51		3600'			filter started leading back to OP.
					Heading into OP radiation

18:03

1808

1813 05

→ LIGHT DRIZZLE.
END OF SCIENCE

405 to 5.
filters off.
entering refueling plane.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 06 may 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
151528																T/o	
151614																Start run 1	
152200	1200	0.1	1	3		0	0	0	0								
152400	1247	0.1	1	3		0	0	0	0								
152600	1200	0.1	1	3		0	0	0	0								
153000	1200	0.1	1	3		0	0	0	0								
153500	1100	0.1	2	3		0	0	0	0								
154000	1200	0.1	2	3		0	0	0	0								
154500	1000	0.1	2	3		0	0	0	0								
155000	900	0.1	3	3		0	0	0	0								
155500	1000	0.09	3	3		0	0	0	0								
155619																End run 1	
155722																Start run 2	
160000	670	0.09	3	3		0	0	0	0								
160500	664	0.09	4	3		0	0	0	0								
160920																End run 2	
161010																Start run 3	
161000	600	0.09	4	3		0	0	0	0								
161500	640	0.09	4	3		0	0	0	0								
162000	700	0.09	4	3		0	0	0	0								
162331																End run 3	
162440																Start run 4	
162500	770	0.09	5	3		0	0	0	0								
163000	1200	0.09	5	3		0	0	0	0								
163500	1000	0.09	5	3		0	0	0	0								
164000	1200	0.09	5	3		0	0	0	0								
164500	750	0.09	6	3		0	0	0	0								
165000	700	0.09	6	3		0	0	0	0								

PCASP Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
			CIP100 End element 64 voltage =

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 06 may 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
165500	860	0.09	6	3		0	0	0	0								
165655																End run 4	
170000	450	0.09	6	3		0	0	0	0							Start of sawtooth	
170300	600	0.09	7	3		0	0	0	0							FI50	
170519	740	0.09	7	3		0	0	0	0							Top of sawtooth	
170810	1000	0.09	7	3		0	0	0	0							FI50	
171000	1100	0.09	7	3		0	0	0	0							End sawtooth	
171000																Start run 5	
171500	600	0.09	7	3		0	0	0	0								
172000	1000	0.09	7	3		0	0	0	0								
172210																End run 5	
172310																Start run 6	
172500	950	0.09	8	3		0	0	0	0								
173000	600	0.1	8	3		0	0	0	0								
173500	550	0.1	8	3		0	0	0	0								
174000	550	0.1	8	3		0	0	0	0								
174500	600	0.1	8	3		0	0	0	0								
175000	510	0.1	8	3		0	0	0	0								
175500	130	0.09	9	3		0	0	0	0								
180000	440	0.1	9	1		0	0	0	0								
180500	265	0.09	9	1		0	0	0	0								
181000	450	0.11	9	3		0	0	0	0							Drops on 2dc	
181500	400	0.1	10	1		0	0	0	0							End science	

PCASP Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
			CIP100 End element 64 voltage =

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B363
Date of flight: 06/05/2008

T/O:
Land:

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of Flight:

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip		Size of Bnnn.dat =
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read =26049 Blocks written = 26059 Bad reads =0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		Start = 0 End = 240000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size? yes
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Data just noise not processed further Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 0 End =240000 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = End =</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B363****Date of Flight:**

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size =1 Vol flow rate = 0.7 0 240000
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check.

P.S.A.P. Log

Flight No. **B.362**.....

Date .6/05/08.....

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FAAM © 2004

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	B _a x 10 ⁻⁶	Ph_det levels	Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time	New filter Tr = 1.000	Set to 3.0 lpm			(30s) ? Ave = s	←Preflight
15:23	1					trans
15:59	1					Sooty had no flow, restart now.
18:08	.880	0				pump off for drizzle.

```

13:59:07.32 --- - - - -
13:59:07.32 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
13:59:07.32 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
13:59:07.32 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B363
13:59:07.32 --- - - - -
13:59:20.38 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:59:20.47 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:59:27.62 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:59:48.59 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
13:59:50.36 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
13:59:52.06 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
13:59:56.43 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
13:59:59.13 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:00:01.96 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
14:00:06.34 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
14:00:06.34 SWS - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
14:00:11.25 USH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
14:00:11.25 USH - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
14:00:14.83 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
14:00:14.84 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
14:00:17.19 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:00:17.19 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:00:17.19 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:00:21.67 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:00:21.71 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:00:21.75 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:00:22.15 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:00:22.50 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:00:22.82 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:00:23.03 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:00:27.71 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:00:28.12 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:00:32.87 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:00:39.32 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:00:39.67 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:00:40.60 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:00:42.10 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:00:43.04 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:01:27.05 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
14:01:30.78 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
14:01:46.65 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
14:02:06.42 SWS -0.0 - - - Telescope sent to 80.000
14:02:07.54 SWS 80.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
14:02:20.78 SWS 80.0 - - - Telescope sent to 150.000
14:02:21.86 SWS 150.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
14:02:31.14 SWS 150.0 - - - Telescope sent to 140.000
15:03:14.55 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:03:14.62 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:03:14.83 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:03:15.14 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:03:15.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:03:15.69 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:03:15.97 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:03:21.60 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:03:24.30 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:03:25.13 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:03:30.80 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:03:32.12 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
15:03:37.86 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:03:44.31 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:15:29.29 USH - - - - Idling
15:15:29.32 SWS - - - - Idling
15:15:29.55 LSH - - - - Idling
15:15:33.69 SWS - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
15:15:33.70 SWS - - - 75 NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
15:15:37.14 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.

```

15:15:37.15	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
15:15:40.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:40.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:40.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:44.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:44.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:44.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:45.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:45.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:50.00	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:15:50.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:15:50.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:55.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:56.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:59.82	USH	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
15:15:59.83	USH	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
15:16:05.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:05.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:05.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:06.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:11.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:11.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:20.80	USH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 40ms.
15:16:20.80	USH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 40ms.
15:16:25.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:25.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:25.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:26.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:26.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:32.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:34.85	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
15:16:34.86	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
15:16:38.14	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
15:16:38.14	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
15:16:43.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:43.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:43.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:44.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:44.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:50.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:51.09	SWS	140.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:16:51.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:16:52.78	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:16:56.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:56.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:57.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:16:58.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:16:58.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:17:03.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:17:18.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:17:20.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:17:24.79	USH	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
15:17:24.80	USH	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
15:17:29.24	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
15:17:29.25	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
15:17:31.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:17:32.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:17:56.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** upper shims VIS module has stopped working
15:18:09.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler box at 3 deg
15:21:23.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
15:22:14.00	---	-	-	-	-	
15:22:14.00	---	-	-	-	-	+++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
15:22:14.00	---	-	-	-	-	+++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment	+++	-	-	-	-	
15:22:14.00	---	-	-	-	-	+++ Flight no. B363
15:22:14.01	---	-	-	-	-	
15:22:30.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
15:22:39.76	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:22:42.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK

15:22:42.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
15:22:42.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
15:22:59.26	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
15:23:01.45	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
15:23:03.53	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
15:23:04.50	LSH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
15:23:06.98	LSH	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:23:06.99	LSH	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:23:08.17	USH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
15:23:10.35	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
15:23:10.36	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
15:23:11.80	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
15:23:14.01	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
15:23:14.01	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
15:23:15.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:15.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:15.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:19.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:19.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:19.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:23:20.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:23:20.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:20.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:23:21.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:21.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:24.73	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:23:26.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:29.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:29.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:29.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:30.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:30.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:35.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:55.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:24:00.45	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
15:24:00.46	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
15:24:05.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:06.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:24:07.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:08.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:30:50.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
15:33:04.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
15:33:38.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
15:36:28.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
15:41:47.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:47.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:47.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:51.14	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:41:52.82	SWS	171.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:41:55.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:55.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:55.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:58.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:58.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:58.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:59.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:41:59.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:59.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:41:59.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:42:00.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:00.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:42:05.22	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:42:05.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:10.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:11.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:13.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:14.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:42:16.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:19.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

15:42:23.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:44:57.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
15:45:32.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
15:47:01.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
15:47:23.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
15:47:50.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** point F4
15:49:19.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:49:19.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:49:19.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:49:19.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:49:21.74	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:49:23.40	SWS	-1.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:49:26.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:26.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:26.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:31.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:31.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:31.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:32.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:32.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:37.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:51:38.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** waypoint F5
15:56:03.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
15:56:30.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 1
15:56:39.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** ascent to 3200 ft
15:57:31.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 2
15:58:09.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
15:58:47.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** waypoint F6
15:59:38.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
16:01:40.98	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:01:45.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:01:45.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:01:45.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:01:46.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:01:46.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:01:52.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:07:25.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
16:08:08.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 2 at F7
16:09:22.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** reached waypoint F7 now (and end of run)
16:10:20.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3 at 3800 ft
16:11:37.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
16:12:46.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:12:46.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:12:46.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:12:49.78	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
16:12:51.45	SWS	169.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:12:53.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:53.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:53.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:58.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:12:59.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:13:00.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:13:01.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:13:03.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:13:10.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:13:34.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
16:14:37.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
16:20:20.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:20:20.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:20:20.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:20:22.55	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:20:24.25	SWS	-4.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:20:26.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:26.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:26.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:29.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:29.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:29.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:30.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

16:20:31.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:36.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:23:21.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
16:23:41.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 3
16:24:28.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
16:24:41.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 4
16:24:46.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2700 ft
16:25:13.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
16:26:26.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
16:26:40.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
16:27:43.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
16:28:04.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
16:30:53.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:53.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:53.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:54.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:54.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:55.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:31:00.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:00.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:45.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** fairly extensive cloud cover
16:35:05.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler box still
16:35:10.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 3 degree
16:35:55.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:35:55.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:35:55.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:35:58.02	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
16:35:59.70	SWS	171.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:36:02.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:02.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:02.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:05.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:36:06.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:08.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:36:09.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:10.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:36:18.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:28.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
16:38:00.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** plume of pollution ?
16:38:05.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
16:38:30.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** leaving plume
16:38:58.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
16:40:06.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** 5 deg
16:40:20.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:40:20.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:40:21.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:40:23.33	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:40:25.08	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:40:26.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:26.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:26.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:37.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
16:40:40.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:41.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:43.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:44.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:46.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:52.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:41:24.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** peltiers 1 and 2 not working efficiently
16:41:45.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** waypoint F8
16:42:19.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud begining to thin towards Melpitz
16:43:06.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** plume from a power station passed
16:43:47.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** so plume which have been sampling is not
the outflow we are after						
16:47:19.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
16:50:23.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** waypoint F9
16:52:02.49	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:52:07.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:52:07.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

16:52:08.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:52:09.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:09.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:14.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:56:47.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning at Melpitz (most northerly point)
16:57:28.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 4
17:00:03.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
17:05:15.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 5 at 8000 ft
17:05:31.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile 1.2 descending
17:06:26.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 degree
17:09:58.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 5
17:10:26.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3700 ft
17:10:32.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:10:32.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:10:32.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:10:33.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:10:33.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:10:38.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:12:08.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:12:08.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:12:08.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:12:10.36	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
17:12:13.65	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
17:12:15.35	SWS	172.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
17:12:17.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:12:17.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:12:17.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:12:20.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:12:20.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:12:20.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:12:21.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:12:21.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:12:27.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:17:13.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
17:18:09.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
17:18:34.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
17:18:58.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
17:23:00.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 5 at 17:22:25
17:23:07.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 6
17:24:04.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 4300 ft
17:28:21.28	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
17:28:21.28	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
17:28:24.99	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
17:28:25.00	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
17:28:28.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:28.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:28.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:29.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:31.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:35.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:49.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:28:49.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:28:49.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:28:51.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:51.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:51.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:29:00.73	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
17:29:00.74	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
17:29:03.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:29:06.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:29:11.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
17:30:31.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
17:30:36.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
17:31:06.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
17:37:21.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:37:21.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:37:21.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:37:23.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:37:23.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

17:37:27.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:39:28.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4000 ft
17:39:48.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud above
17:40:56.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
17:42:13.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
17:43:48.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
17:49:00.85	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:49:06.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:49:06.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:49:07.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:49:09.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:49:09.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:49:13.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:54:51.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3600 ft
17:55:58.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
17:56:33.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg
17:57:02.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:57:02.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:57:02.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:57:06.82	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
17:57:08.49	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
17:57:10.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:10.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:10.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:17.89	USH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
17:57:17.90	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
17:57:23.40	USH	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 600ms.
17:57:23.41	USH	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 600ms.
17:57:26.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:27.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:27.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:29.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:33.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:33.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:59:46.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:59:46.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:59:46.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:59:47.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:59:49.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:59:53.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:59:53.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:59:59.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:06:54.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** getting dark -
18:07:35.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** light precip
18:10:22.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:10:22.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:10:22.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:10:24.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:10:29.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:10:29.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:10:45.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg
18:11:55.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** 4 deg
18:12:18.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3 deg

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No. **B**...363.....

Date ..6/5/08.....

Operator's name:S. Bowles.....

Page1. of 2.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
1524	1		17	35	40.5	↑45		
1530ish						↓15		TRY TO FIX SOOTY!
1546						↑45		
								SOOTY FIXED 1558
1558	2		16.7	34%	33%	↓15		≈ 1.4 @ 80%
1603	2		16.7	32.1	50.6	↑45		
160920	↑							
16:1040	3	3800						
16:14	3	"	16.4	27%	35%	↓15		≈ 1.4 > 1.5 @ 85% - NOISY
16:19	"	"	16.4	29.2	51%	↑45		
16:23:51	↓	2700						
16:24:40	4	2700						
16:28					85%	↓16		≈ 1.3 @ 85% - NOISY
16:31	"	"	17.0	36	52%	↑46		
16:37			16.9	37.3	37%	↓16		≈ 1.6 @ 85% - TIGHT SIGNAL
16:42						↑35		
16:47				27.5	67%	↑46		
16:52			16.9	24.6	35%	↓16		≈ 1.3 @ 85% - BIT NOISY
16:55						↑		CHILLER LOCKED UP. POWER CYCLE
17:59:50	↑		16.4	24	50%	↑46		Leave @ 85% For SAWTOOTH PROFILES

Flight:

B363

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Hygrometers

Cameras

Navigation + Aircraft

Misc Core

Radiometers

Cloud Probes

Aerosol

Chemistry

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B363

Date: 06 May 2008

Instruments

1. INU – not responding to serial commands. Changed Terminal server (HORNET) for HOUSEFLY.
2. FFC – smudges on camera window appeared in flight, probably insects – inform Avalon post-flight
3. CGPS – new software installed but CGPS still doesn't work.
4. PSAP – no flow shortly after T/O, reading 0.2slpm. Suspect loose wire to MFC inside PSAP. Try to open up PSAP box with in-flight toolkit to inspect. Fixed problem, flow resumed at 1558Z
5. CAMCON - software in FAAM software pack won't run. Error on startup "Cannot find VB40016.dll"

Instrument Status roundup

Nephys and Filters okay.

AMS – lost sensitivity for a couple of hours before end of flight

SMPS fine at low level, no use at altitude

CCN – minor problem with software, re-installed it then okay, CPC okay too

PAN/WAS/Core Chem – no was, core chem. okay, tdlas data suspect, pan data suspect

CAPS/SP2/CPI – CPI not run, SP2 and CAPS (though no cloud to test it fully) okay.

Cloud Physics – 2DC fine 2DP noisy, PCASP fine sid 1 & ffssp fine

SWS – Lost upper shims for 10 mins at start otherwise fine

Aircraft

1. Intercom – speech, especially on Flt I/C distorted. Training channel also distorted with warbling noises
- 2.

ISDN Emails

1 connection at 1542Z for approx 1 minute to check for received messages. Nil received

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B363:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
2D-S / CAPS / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
CVI	No log was taken for this flight
PAN	No log available

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	12 Jun 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras

2 x Upward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080506_b363_151148_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080506_b363_161148_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080506_b363_171148_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080506_b363_181148_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080506_b363_151139_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080506_b363_161139_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080506_b363_171139_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080506_b363_181139_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080506_b363_151137_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080506_b363_161137_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080506_b363_171137_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080506_b363_181137_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080506_b363_151144_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080506_b363_161144_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080506_b363_171144_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080506_b363_181144_1hz.avi

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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